

Impact of Deforestation and Forest Degradation on Soil Carbon Dynamics in Subtropical Pine Forest in District Buner, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

Carbon sequestration in forest soil and vegetation is one of the key approaches to reducing atmospheric carbon concentrations. The estimation of biomass and carbon stock in a forest is crucial for understanding the dynamics of the ecosystem. The present study deals with the estimation of carbon stock in standing trees and soil in the Chir Pine forest in Buner district, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Carbon stock (along with other basic parameters, i.e., pH, moisture content, temperature, electrical conductivity, and organic matter) of the soils of standing trees and degraded forests in different categories (%) was estimated. The pH of all collected samples was based on the degradation of the forest. The graph shows that pH is higher in deforested soil (DS), followed by the 50% degraded forest soil (50% DFS), then dense forest (DF), followed by the 10% degraded forest soil (10% DFS) and 25% degraded forest soil (25% DFS). The electrical conductivity (EC) was found in the range of 10% DFS > DF > 25% DFS > 50% DFS > DS. Similarly, the temperature of the soil was measured during sampling at the selected spots in the forest. The graph shows higher values for 25% degraded forest soil and 50% degraded forest soil, followed by 10% degraded forest soil, dense forest soil, and degraded forest soil. Moisture content was in the sequence from higher to lower as 25% DFS > 50% DFS > 10% DFS > DS > DF. The average organic matter (OM) was in the sequence of 10% DFS > DF > 25% DFS > DS > 50% DFS. The highest organic carbon content was found in the soil from the 25% degraded forest soil (DFS), followed by the 10% degraded forest soil, then the dense forest soil (DFS), the 50% degraded forest soil, and finally the deforested soil (DS). Hence, it is proven that forests are the main body for organic carbon. Forests can sequester a significant amount of carbon as they act as the largest sink for it. It is recommended to conserve forests both in situ and ex situ, and to protect them from degradation by all means.

Keywords: Deforestation, Degradation, Carbon Dynamics, Chir Pine, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric carbon concentration is mainly reduced because of carbon sequestration in forest soil and vegetation (Sharma et al., 2011). In the forest, the assessment of biomass and carbon storage is essential for understanding the dynamics of the

ecosystem. Vegetation and soil are among the primary factors that play a significant role in global climate change and the carbon cycle. The primary source of carbon is the stored carbon in forests, which contains a large amount of carbon. This carbon is disturbed by human activities and natural causes, but it turns out to be a sink during re-growth after instabilities (Hurteau et al., 2019). The capacity of carbon storage in organic material is a sign of climate quality, availability of nutrients, and soil structure (Waqas et al., 2020). Forests in the Central Himalaya, *Pinus roxburghii* Sarg., are the main vegetation in the area between 1000 m and 1800 m. Chir pine forests, when compared with mixed forests in the area, are noted to be less diverse (Kumar et al., 2021). Timber and resin industries obtain a cherished resource from the chir pine forests. Chir pine forest has high economic importance, and thus, in many areas, monoculture plantations of chir pine have been planted (Negi et al., 2025).

The assessment of biomass helps make decisions for managing forests (Herold et al., 2019). The mature tree, which has a greater diameter, has the capacity to store large quantities of biomass, so the specific girth class classification of trees plays a significant role in the estimation of forest carbon and tree biomass (Young trees). In the woody biomass of trees with a diameter in the range of 20-49.99 cm, nearly 74% of aboveground carbon was sequestered, and in trees with a diameter between 20-29.99 cm and 40-49.99 cm, the sequestration rates were recorded as higher at 0.95 tons/ha/year and 0.62 tons/ha/year, respectively, representing 71% of the annual forest sequestration rate (Adhikari et al., 2011). In the plantation forest in the 40-60 cm diameter class and the 60-80 cm dbh class in the natural forest, the biomass was also recorded as greater (Khan et al., 2020). Trees remove CO₂ from the air via photosynthesis, and carbon is stored in different parts of plants. In the dry weight of tree biomass, almost half is carbon content. The primary approach to offsetting carbon dioxide emissions is to expand forest areas and plant more trees. For carbon dioxide absorbance from the air, natural and planted forests work as 'sinks.' Capturing and storing atmospheric CO₂ in biomass products, soil, and vegetation mainly depends on tree growth (Whitehead, 2011). Though significant differences exist between forests and similar forests at altered latitudes (Schmidt et al., 2000).

Under the trees, a forest was cultivated for agroforestry. Soil characteristics such as mean weight diameter, aggregate uniformity coefficient, bulk density, organic matter, potassium, nitrogen, pH, EC, phosphorus, soluble cations and anions, tilth index, plasticity, and index were examined. Deforestation and tillage practices increased bulk density (20%) and caused a decline in organic matter (50%) and total nitrogen when compared with undisturbed soil; a decrease of 10-15% in soluble ions was also noted. Comparing the tilth index coefficient between deforested areas and cultivated forests, the tilth index (three-depth average of the site in the forest) was found to be considerably higher. The lower quality of forest soil is due to clear-cutting and deforestation, which results in declining natural soil productivity (Tegegne et al., 2017). Global climate change and the carbon cycle are affected by vegetation and soil.

Therefore, the main purpose of the current study was to evaluate the carbon sequestration potential of Chir Pine (*Pinus roxburghii*) trees on the slopes of Buner District in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, which included both soil and forests. In particular, the research attempted to make an estimate of carbon stock in various

conditions of the forest, i.e., dense forest, partially degraded forest, and areas where all the forest has been deforested. Another purpose of the study was to investigate the impact of forest degradation on soil carbon content, focusing on key soil characteristics such as pH, moisture content, temperature, electrical conductivity (EC), and organic matter (OM). Through the comparison of such parameters with different grades of forest degradation, the research aimed at determining the trends and patterns that may affect the capability of the soil in terms of carbon holding. The final goal was to develop baseline research data that can be used in conservation practices in the forest, show the ecological relevance of Chir Pine forests, as well as mitigate climate change through a better appreciation of carbon sequestration potential in forested terrain.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

The current study has been carried out in the wake of the District Buner in the territory of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan (Figure 1). The district is located at 34°23'39.42"N 72°36'54.42"E and spans approximately 1,865 km² (GOP, 2017). The Pakistan Bureau of Statistics (2017) Census revealed that the district has a density of 271 persons per km², and the total population of the district is above 895,460 persons. District Buner is a mountainous area with a number of prolific valleys, streams, and irrigation canals, including the Chamla Canal, Barandu, and the Totalai canals. The territory is located adjacent to Swat to the north, with the Ilam Range and the Mora Mountains to the northeast, Malakand to the west, and Mardan to the south (Ullah et al., 2025). On an administrative level, Buner is further subdivided into seven tehsils and 27 Union Councils, with the district headquarters in Daggar.

The weather in the area is categorized as humid subtropical, with four distinct seasons: spring, summer, autumn, and winter. Winters (November to February) are comparatively cold, with intermittent snow at higher elevations (Gadezai and Elum mountains), while summer is moderately hot, promoting farming (Ullah et al., 2025). Buner has incredible biodiversity, especially among the aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems of this region. It contains open, running, and standing water bodies, forested hills, and grasslands that support numerous flora and fauna, making it ecologically significant compared to other districts in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (WWF-Pakistan, 2021).

Pashto is the primary language, and among the ethnic groups are the Yousafzai, Gujjar, and Chagharzai tribes. The socio-economic organization is rural and agrarian. Subsistence agriculture, herding, and the sale of forest products are the main building blocks of the local economy, with the majority of the population involved in these activities (FAO, 2019). The region was previously part of the princely state of Swat before joining Pakistan in 1969, and it became a district of its own in 1970 (GOP, 2018).

DATA COLLECTION

Two types of data were collected in this research: primary data and secondary data.

Figure 1. The GIS Map of the study area.

Primary data

Primary data were collected from sample plots. In each sample plot, data were collected on soil slope, aspect, elevation, and forest density. Soil samples were collected from the centers of nested circular plots randomly laid out in forest areas. At a depth of 30 cm, soil was used for the procedure, and a soil auger with a diameter of 6 cm and a length of 30 cm was used for digging purposes. Samples of the soil were air-dried for seven days in the lab. Twigs and stones were removed, then ground and passed through a sieve with a pore size of less than 2 mm. After sieving, the samples were stored in properly labeled plastic bags for analysis. Soil samples were weighed with a digital balance on the spot. The samples were labeled and transferred to the Forest Chemistry Laboratory branch of the Pakistan Forest Institute (PFI), Peshawar. The samples were oven-dried, and their weights were recorded after drying at 105°, as shown in Table 1.

Secondary data

Secondary data were collected from research journals, books, and government websites. Agencies and international organizations.

Table 1: Showing Weight of the Soil Samples throughout the Lab Analysis

Sample code	Fresh wt. (g)	Dish wt. (g)	Soil sample (50 g)	Dry wt. of sample taken	After ignition wt. (dish + soil)
1	548	86.11	50	132.03	131.04
2	462	92.82	50	139.25	138.20
3	362	96.19	50	141.38	139.13
4	432	89.57	50	135.22	133.94
5	414	90.16	50	134.91	132.77
6	446	93.03	50	138.80	137.01
7	268	86.50	50	130.70	128.69
8	644	90.22	50	135.22	133.92
9	268	93.40	50	136.45	134.97
10	278	85.18	50	129.30	127.96
11	210	90.20	50	136.74	135.42
12	418	89.21	50	132.78	131.60
13	638	83.38	50	126.61	125.06
14	222	88.74	50	127.04	123.23
15	206	86.82	50	132.80	131.14
16	218	82.63	50	125.22	122.78
17	178	49.77	50	94.18	92.46
18	526	53.79	50	92.90	88.12
19	208	62.82	50	103.44	100.71
20	198	53.87	50	93.42	88.59
21	400	53.05	50	95.35	93.66
22	234	51.50	50	97.83	96.96
23	318	86.59	50	91.64	89.41
24	248	52.49	50	97.96	96.57
25	234	51.80	50	93.70	91.58
26	186	48.93	50	96.09	94.16
27	310	50.55	50	93.98	91.55
28	630	51.01	50	91.98	89.52
29	216	45.25	50	87.21	82.91
30	320	50.75	50	93.81	90.68
31	610	49.06	50	93.72	92.52
32	506	58.06	50	103.58	102.50
33	374	93.32	50	141.36	140.76
34	366	86.74	50	131.36	129.79
35	690	83.32	50	128.45	127.2
36	576	85.10	50	131.65	30.36
37	442	92.93	50	138.42	137.12
38	518	82.58	50	127.65	126.11
39	548	86.44	50	131.08	129.74
40	650	90.15	50	137.49	136.67
41	182	86.08	50	132.66	131.10

42	206	88.49	50	134.40	131.47
43	246	96.05	50	142.79	141.58
44	372	90.09	50	138.31	137.14
45	202	92.74	50	142.29	140.26
46	378	89.51	50	134.84	133.23
47	252	88.65	50	136.25	134.97
48	476	89.06	50	136.98	136.17
49	394	57.90	50	105.73	104.86
50	408	52.39	50	101.01	100.25

Determination of aspect, elevation, and crown cover

Aspects of the samples were determined using a compass, elevation was found using GPS, and crown cover was estimated through visual observation. The locations of the sample plots were also determined using GPS. All these parameters were recorded on the data collection form.

pH of the soil samples

The pH of the samples was determined using the methodology of McLean (1982). In this method, soil (10 g) was placed in a conical flask (250 ml), and distilled water (50 ml) was added to create a 1:5 soil-to-water suspension. A mechanical shaker (“Edmund Buhler GmbH”) was used to shake the suspension at 150 rpm for half an hour. After performing the pH calibration, the suspension was examined for pH. The calibrations were maintained for 4.7 and 9.2 buffers using a ‘Coring’ (model No. 7) pH meter.

EC

EC of soils was determined using the methodology described by Rhoades (1996). A soil sample (10 g) was placed in a conical flask (250 mL), and distilled water (50 mL) was mixed in to prepare soil-water (1:5) suspensions. A mechanical shaker, “Edmund Buhler GmbH,” was used for the suspension for 30 minutes at 150 rpm. Filtration was then performed using Whatman filter paper No. 42. The EC of the filtrate was examined using an “Electrolytic Conductivity Cell” (model EBB/10). pH measurements and EC parameters provided valuable information for assessing soil conditions, nutrient cycling for plant growth, and other biological activities.

Determination of soil organic matter

For the determination of soil organic matter in the soil, the method of loss on ignition was used. The instruments used in this method were an electric balance, crucible, oven, furnace, and desiccator.

First, the crucible was weighed, then the crucible was filled with soil and reweighed. Thus, the weight of the soil taken in the crucible was determined. The sample was oven-dried at 105 °C for 24 hours. After that, the sample was weighed, then the sample was put in a muffle furnace at 550 °C for 8 hours to burn the organic matter. After that, the final weight of the ash was noted. The following formula calculates the organic matter.

$$\text{Organic matter} = \text{weight of oven-dried sample} - \text{weight of ash}$$

Determination of soil organic Carbon

Soil organic carbon was determined by converting the soil organic matter through the formula given below:

$$\text{Organic carbon (g)} = \text{organic matter (g)} \times 0.58$$

$$\text{Organic carbon} = \text{organic matter (\%)} \times 0.58.$$

The organic carbon was converted to per-hectare estimates by multiplying the organic carbon content (mg/g of soil particles) by soil bulk density.

RESULTS

Table 1 presents the results of the analyzed soil samples collected from various forest conditions. The pH (1:5) of the incubated soil was measured at multiple sites, revealing that the pH levels varied according to the degree of forest degradation. Figure 2 shows that pH was highest in Deforested Soil (DS), followed by 50 percent Degraded Forest Soil (50% DFS), Dense Forest (DF), 10 percent DFS, and 25 percent DFS. The overall samples can be ranked in order of pH values from highest to lowest as follows: DS > 50% DFS > DF > 10% DFS > 25% DFS (Figure 8).

Electrical Conductivity (EC) values, as indicated in Figure 3, were observed to be the highest in 10% Degraded Forest Soil, followed by Dense Forest Soil, 25% DFS, 50% DFS, and the lowest in Deforested Soil. The rank of EC is as follows: 10% DFS > DF > 25% DFS > 50% DFS > DS. The overall average EC values are shown in Figure 9 and Figure 4 indicates the temperature of the soil recordings during the collection of the samples. Temperatures in the soil peaked in 25% DFS and 50% DFS, followed by 10% DFS, DF, and DS. The overall average temperature values are shown in Figure 10. The soil moisture content, as shown in Figure 5 and table 2, was the highest in 10% DFS, then it decreased in DF, 25% DFS, and 50% DFS, with the lowest in DS. The moisture content sequence was as follows for all samples: DFS > 10% DFS > 25% DFS > 50% DFS > DS. The overall average moisture content values are shown in Figure 11.

Physical and chemical analyses revealed that the highest organic matter content, as shown in Figure 6, was found in 10% DFS, followed by DF, 25% DFS, and DS, with the lowest content in 50% DFS. The order of organic matter content was as follows: DFS, 10% DFS, DF, 25% DFS, DS, and 50% DFS. The overall average organic matter values are displayed in Figure 12. Data on organic carbon content is presented in Figure 7, indicating that the highest concentration of organic carbon was in 25% DFS, followed by 10% DFS, 50% DFS, and the lowest in DS. The reported range for organic carbon content was DFS > 25% DFS > 10% DFS > 50% DFS > DS. The overall average organic carbon values are shown in Figure 13.

Table 2: Showing pH, Electrical Conductivity, Temperature, Moisture Content, Organic Matter, and Organic Carbon of the Soil taken from the Different Locations of Chirpine Forest in District Buner, KP, Pakistan

Sample type	Sample code	pH	EC ($\mu\text{S/cm}$)	Temp ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Moisture content (g)	Organic matter (g)	Organic carbon (g)
	1.	6.69	569	26.5	4.08	0.99	0.5742
	2.	6.42	513	26.5	3.57	1.05	0.609

25% Degraded Forest Soil	3.	6.72	501	26.6	4.81	2.25	1.305
	4.	7.31	512	26.6	4.35	1.28	0.7424
	5.	6.46	562	26.3	5.25	2.14	1.2412
	6.	6.82	609	26.5	4.17	1.79	1.0382
	7.	6.51	621	26.7	6.80	2.01	1.1658
	8.	7.67	503	26.3	5.00	1.3	0.754
	9.	6.48	505	26.5	3.75	1.48	0.8584
	10.	6.91	619	26.4	5.88	1.34	0.7772
Average		6.79	551.4	26.49	4.76	1.56	0.906
10% Degraded Soil	11.	6.21	601	26.4	3.46	1.32	0.7656
	12.	6.89	613	26.4	6.43	1.18	0.6844
	13.	6.83	634	26.4	6.77	1.55	0.899
	14.	6.71	701	26.6	11.7	3.81	2.2098
	15.	6.11	618	26.6	4.02	1.66	0.9628
	16.	6.16	660	26.4	7.51	2.44	1.4152
	17.	6.67	623	25.4	5.59	1.72	0.9976
	18.	6.91	681	25.4	10.89	4.79	2.7782
	19.	6.96	602	25.3	9.38	2.73	1.5834
	20.	6.91	668	25.3	10.45	4.83	2.8014
Average		6.63	640.1	26.02	7.62	2.603	1.509
Dense Forest Soil	21.	6.94	543	25.3	7.7	1.69	0.9802
	22.	7.02	622	25.2	3.67	0.8	0.464
	23.	7.11	641	24.9	4.95	2.23	1.2934
	24.	7.27	671	25.4	4.53	1.39	0.8062
	25.	7.31	591	25.4	8.1	2.12	1.2296
	26.	7.06	636	24.9	2.84	1.93	1.1194
	27.	7.83	642	24.7	6.57	2.43	1.4094
	28.	6.71	556	27.1	9.03	2.46	1.4628
	29.	6.26	607	27.1	11.04	4.3	2.494
	30.	7.11	527.9	27.3	6.94	3.13	1.8154
Average		7.06	603.69	25.73	6.537	2.248	1.307
50% Degraded Soil	31.	6.89	17.87	27.5	5.33	1.2	0.696
	32.	6.67	35.02	27.3	4.48	1.08	0.6264
	33.	6.91	17.52	25.8	1.96	0.6	0.348
	34.	7.17	22.3	26.5	5.34	1.61	0.9338
	35.	7.21	10.25	26.3	4.87	1.23	0.7134
	36.	7.25	26.1	26.9	3.45	1.29	0.7482
	37.	6.31	34.4	26.7	4.51	1.54	0.8932
	38.	6.78	36.1	25.4	4.93	1.27	0.7366
	39.	7.12	33.7	26.2	5.36	1.34	0.7772
	40.	7.81	31.7	26.3	2.66	0.82	0.4756
Average		7.01	26.49	26.49	4.289	1.198	0.694
	41.	7.34	23.0	26.9	3.4	1.5	0.87
	42.	7.28	6.95	25.2	4.09	2.93	1.7284

Deforested Soil	43.	6.91	17.69	25.3	3.26	1.21	0.7018
	44.	7.72	7.34	25.4	1.78	1.17	0.6786
	45.	6.93	13.51	26.7	0.45	2.03	1.1774
	46.	6.83	5.04	26.4	4.67	1.61	0.9338
	47.	7.21	11.31	25.1	2.4	1.28	0.7424
	48.	7.72	17.88	26.1	2.08	0.81	0.1044
	49.	6.82	25.3	26.8	2.17	0.87	0.5046
	50.	7.52	32.2	26.5	1.38	0.76	0.4403
Average	7.228	16.022	26.04	2.568	1.417	0.788	

Figure 2: pH of the ten selected samples from 25% degraded forest soil.

Figure 3: EC(μ S/cm) of the ten selected samples from a 25% degraded forest.

Figure 4: Temperature ($^{\circ}$ C) of the ten selected samples of 25% degraded forest.

Figure 5: Moisture Content (g) of the ten selected samples of 25% degraded forest.

Figure 6: Organic Matter(g) of the ten selected samples of 25% degraded forest.

Figure 7: Organic Carbon (g) of the ten selected samples of 25% degraded forest.

Figure 8: Overall average pH of the soil taken from all of the plots of the selected areas.

Figure 9: Overall average EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) of the soil taken from all of the plots of the selected areas.

Figure 10: Overall average temperature of the soil taken from all of the plots of the selected areas.

Figure 11: Overall average moisture content (g) of the soil taken from all of the plots of the selected areas.

Figure 12: Overall average Organic Matters (g) of the soil taken from all of the plots of the selected areas.

Figure 13: Overall average Organic Carbon (g) of the soil taken from all of the plots of the selected areas.

DISCUSSION

The pH of the soil is vital to the availability of soil nutrients and soil chemistry. A clear pattern associated with the extent of forest degradation can be observed in the pH values of incubated soil samples. Higher to lower pH values were recorded in the following order: Deforested Soil (DS) > 50% Degraded Forest Soil (50% DFS) > Dense Forest (DF) > 10% Degraded Forest Soil (10% DFS) > 25% Degraded Forest Soil (25% DFS). This trend indicates that, despite the magnitude of degradation, soil pH was primarily raised, with the worst degradation (lack of a forest) and medium degradation sites (50%) recording the highest values.

The high pH in DS and 50% DFS aligns with various research studies on the effects of deforestation. The pH of the soil is relatively acidic to neutral. This is due to the constant addition of acidic organic litter through litterfall, the formation of organic acids during organic decomposition, and the leaching of basic cations in forest ecosystems (Beheshti et al., 2019; Ustaoglu et al., 2024). All these processes are disturbed when forests are cut. Decomposition of the existing organic matter can be expedited by the termination of the input of acidic litter, accompanied by increased sun exposure and elevated temperatures in the ground. This rapid mineralization may result in the release of basic cations, which further increases the soil pH (Gulser et al., 2021). In addition, the clearance of vegetation cover may also change the leaching of nutrients, resulting in the accumulation of some basic ions in the topsoil, which can lead to an increase in alkalinity.

On the other hand, the pH of the 10% and 25% Degraded Forest Soil (DFS) sites shows a significant drop when compared with that of the Dense Forest (DF), thus highlighting the need to carry out additional research on this topic. Although full deforestation usually causes pH to rise, early or incomplete degradation has the potential to trigger other biogeochemical reactions. During the initial phases of forest disturbance, selective logging or partial clearing may result in an initial acceleration in the rate of decomposition of organic material, which may release a pulse of organic acids or otherwise affect the community structure of the microbes in a manner that facilitates acidification (Wang et al., 2024). It may also be influenced by the types of vegetation that survive or recover in these semi-degraded areas, or by local gradients of soil aeration and wetness, which influence microbial activity. There is also the possibility that some canopy cover will not be completely removed; however, this will still mean that the soil may receive more rainfall, causing some basic cations to

be leached out. Compared to the dense forest, the pH will be relatively lower. The Dense Forest (DF) pH serves as a reference, representing a relatively stable and mature ecosystem with the retention of organic matter and nutrients in the soil. It should be noted that the impact of deforestation on soil pH may be rather complicated and situation-specific, depending on the initial soil type, climate, as well as the length of the degradation process and the type of land use that occurred after deforestation (Poorter et al., 2023). Although it is reported that areas where deforestation has occurred show acidification, especially in climates where intensive agriculture is additionally introduced or highly eroded land has occurred (Beheshti et al., 2019), in our case, the results indicate that the removal of forest influence initially caused the pH to rise in the most degraded conditions. In contrast, intermediate degradation suggests a much more perceptive reaction.

Electrical conductivity (EC) values, which depict the quantity of soluble salts and fundamental ions in the soil, painted a clear picture: 10% DFS > DF > 25% DFS > 50% DFS > DS. This series shows that the Dense Forest came second in having the highest EC, followed by the moderately degraded (10% DFS), with EC levels decreasing with increasing degradation, and the lowest in the entirely deforested soil. DFS 10% and DF have relatively high EC, implying that nutrients are actively utilized and that the pool of available ions is healthy. In a dense forest setting, there is constant decomposition of leaf litter and other organic remains that create a continuous provision of critical nutrients to the soil solution, which enhances the increase in EC (NRCS, 2022). The trend of increasing EC in 10% DFS compared to DF was noteworthy, as the EC increase was slight, possibly indicating a short-term nutrient flush. This may occur when the first disturbance, in a mild form, speeds up the breakdown of any organic matter present, rendering the nutrients more easily available in the soil solution before the profound influences of leaching or forward drift can take place. It may also measure a stage when the emission/absorption of nutrients is altered, so that excess soluble ions become temporarily accumulated (Chhabra et al., 2022).

The tendency of EC to rise to 25% DFS, 50% DFS, and DS, similar to the discouraging effects of deforestation on soil fertility in the literature, is noteworthy. The destruction of vegetation cover causes a decrease in organic matter import, which is one of the primary sources of nutrients (Powlson et al., 2022). In addition, the soil will be easier to leach and experience surface run-off, carrying with it soluble salts and vital nutrients. Water infiltration can also be reduced through soil compaction, a process commonly associated with land clearing and degradation, which in turn alters the transport of nutrients (Bateman et al., 2019). The reduced EC of Deforested Soil (DS) is a clear indicator of a critical shortage of available nutrients, resulting in significantly reduced soil fertility. Consequently, these lands are less productive and more susceptible to degradation. This loss highlights the fact that forest cover is imperative in perpetuating the chemical diversity and nutrient cycling potential of soil ecosystems (Mandal et al., 2025).

Soil temperature records collected during the sampling period indicated that the highest temperatures were found in the 25% and 50% disturbed forest sites (DFS), followed by a decrease in the 10% DFS, disturbed forest (DF), and disturbed site (DS). The temperatures were ranked as follows: 25% DFS, approximately 50% DFS,

10% DFS, DF, and DS. This trend shows a significant increase in soil temperature, along with a slight decline. Forest canopies play a crucial role in trapping solar radiation and reducing the amount of direct sunlight that reaches the forest floor, which helps maintain cooler and more stable soil temperatures (Feng et al., 2024). In areas with reduced canopy cover, such as the 25% and 50% DFS, direct solar radiation is more likely to reach the ground, leading to increased heat absorption and a subsequent rise in soil temperatures (Xian et al., 2024).

The lower temperatures recorded in the Dense Forest (DF) are predictable due to the severe shading provided by the full canopy. Of course, the overall temperature in Deforested Soil (DS) is rather low compared to the sites with moderate degradation (25% and 50% DFS). Since the complete removal of vegetation cover mostly results in increased soil temperature due to direct exposure to sunlight, other factors may have contributed to the observation in DS. Surface temperature may be cooled by evaporation as a result of increased wind exposure in totally deforested regions. Additionally, the albedo of the surface, as bare soil replaces vegetation, may be a cause; lighter-colored bare soil is more likely to reflect more solar radiation than a partially vegetated degraded site, resulting in slightly cooler surface temperatures. It may also be the case that the absence of a thick litter layer at DS, which could serve as an insulator, contributes to a lower rate of heat dissipation (Zhang et al., 2022).

The moisture contents in the soil also showed the following pattern: 10% DFS (highest), DF > 25% DFS > 50% DFS > DS (lowest). The fact that 10% DFS had the richest soil moisture content is a significant outlier that deviates from a mere linear degradation. Although dense forests are widely known to preserve higher moisture content in the soil due to canopy interception of precipitation, low evapotranspiration, and high organic content, the elevated moisture in 10% DFS might be the result of a simple combination of parameters. There is a possibility that a shallow level of thinning (10% degradation) would decrease canopy transpiration more than it increases direct evaporation from the soil surface, resulting in a net effect of increasing soil water availability. Moreover, adequate microtopography or the soil textural features at the 10% DFS location may contribute to greater water retention (Metzger et al., 2017).

The overall downward trend in soil moisture content between DF and 25% DFS, 50% DFS and finally to the lowest in DS is quite a balanced trend that concurred well with standard ecological principles. The cutting down of trees destroys the hydrological cycle. The above elimination of the protective cover causes an instance of increased direct evaporation of the surface of soil as well as a decrease of rainfall interception, and less water is infiltrated in the soil (Jafari et al., 2022). Moreover, the water-holding capacity of soil is significantly reduced by the loss of organic matter, which acts as a sponge that stores water. Porosity and infiltration rates can also be decreased by compaction of soil due to the degradation process, which increases surface run-off and reduces the amount of water that is added to the soil profile (Bahddou et al., 2023). The importance of the adverse effect of forest clearing on the soil's water holding capacity is highlighted by the fact that the lowest moisture value of DS was obtained, and all these areas are more prone to drought and erosion.

Organic matter (OM) and organic carbon (OC) content are basic measures of the soil fertility and its properties as well as carbon sequestering potential. OM results

gave the following sequence: 10 % DFS (lowest) DF, 25% DFS, DS, 50% DFS (highest). In OC, the maximum was found in 25% DFS, then 10% DFS and DF, 50% DFS, and the minimum in DS, with the ranking being: 25% DFS > 10% DFS > DF > 50% DFS > DS.

The most OM in 10% DFS is a great outcome that warrants consideration. Although dense forests would have high OM since there is a constant litterfall and root materials, such an observation indicates that an insignificant level of degradation would, in the initial stage, result in organic matter build-up. It may be due to an acute surplus in litterfall in the stressed trees or an increase in the decomposition rate, wherein decomposition temporarily falls behind input (Sarkar et al., 2024). newer than the 10 % DFS site possessed elevated OM levels before that, or that the soils had certain features which could offset early losses. However, the further decrease in OM between DF and DS, and the poorest OM in 50% DFS, definitely proves the negative impact of the increasing degradation on the organic matter accretion. Deposits of forest soils are mainly made of organic matter in forests. The degradation and deforestation processes lower the contributions of leaf litter and root biomass to the soil at the same time as increasing the rate at which available organic matter is broken down by expansion (exposure), increased temperatures, and the influence of microbial communities (Samuel et al., 2023). The OM in 50% DFS, remarkably low and even more so when compared with DS, is an acute negative indicator, highly likely to signify that decomposition processes are underway with maximum activity here, or that at this point the practice of land-use has used up organic stores to a perilous length (Mirzabaev et al., 2023).

Organic carbon (OC) also showed an interesting pattern, with the strongest concentration at 25% DFS. This conclusion is the indication that, in certain circumstances, a moderate extent of degradation can cause a temporary increase or re-distribution of organic carbon. Those may be due to numerous variables: microbial community succession, which temporarily boosts carbon stabilization, growth of root exudates of new growing vegetation, or storage of carbon in soil form (Wang et al., 2021). Nevertheless, the general pattern of consumption of DF to DS, in which the DFS has half the prevalence of DF, DS, and the lowest OC levels in all, can be related to the well-known effects of deforestation on soil carbon stocks. The soils in forests are major carbon sinks that help in the storage of vast levels of organic carbon. Deforestation brings the soil into contact with sunlight and higher temperatures, which enhances the disintegration of organic compounds under the influence of microbial activity, affecting the production of CO₂ (Sensoy et al., 2024). Moreover, carbon loss is also possible due to soil erosion, which is often aggravated as a result of deforestation. The minimal OC at DS emphasizes a massive decrease in the capacity of the soil to sequester carbon after the total deforestation (Amoakwah et al., 2022).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The result indicates maximum moisture composition in dense forests, followed by other selected regions. Furthermore, there is an apparent decline in organic carbon in deforested soils of Chir pine forests in District Buner, in contrast to the maximum organic carbon found in dense forests. This simply indicates that the forest is the real

source of carbon. It resulted in a significant mass of carbon in its biomass. The declined forest biomass, which was degraded by the soil, consists of this content. The main idea was to mitigate climate change by incentivizing developing countries to maintain their forests, as carbon emissions are a key driver of deforestation. It has an expanded scope and presently includes deforestation, conservation, forest degradation, enhancement of forest carbon stocks, and sustainable management of forests in developing countries, collectively called REDD+. One of the significant facts is that soils and vegetation cover play a vital role in the global carbon cycle and climate change as well. The biomass and carbon stock estimation helps in decision-making for the management of the forest. Our study, along with many similar studies, has documented that Chir pine forests sequester significant amounts of carbon. This information will prominently help in effective ecosystem management. Our study provided a similar scenario where higher biomass was accumulated in the mature trees of the 111-160 cm girth class and the 64-110 cm girth class, respectively. This emphasizes the conservation and protection of mature natural forests, which act as a carbon sink.

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Conflict of interests

There is no conflict of interest declare by the authors.

Ethical approval

This research did not entail any experiment carried out on human beings or animals that would need ethical certification.

Informed consent

Not applicable. There were no human subjects in this study.

Authors contribution

HY proposed the main concept and involved in write up, SY supervised the whole research and manuscript work, AS and MZ provided basic facilities for the collection of samples and field data, and performed chemical analysis of the samples, BBK helped in data analysis, MM and MLS revised the manuscript critically for important intellectual content, and AR and NAA read and approved the final manuscript.

Data Availability Statement

This published article includes all the data that was generated or analyzed during this research work. Further data are to be obtained from the corresponding author upon request in a reasonable extent.

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